

1 **Cyclopeptide alkaloids from the Greek shrub *Paliurus spina-christi* and**
2 **their *in silico* binding affinity to Dipeptidyl Peptidase IV**

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13 Cyclopeptide alkaloids from the Greek shrub *Paliurus spina-christi* and 14 their *in-silico* binding affinity to Dipeptidyl Peptidase IV

15 A new cyclopeptide alkaloid, spinachristene A (**1**), along with two previously
16 described, sanjoinenine (**2**) and oxyphylline C (**3**), were isolated from the fruits of
17 *Paliurus spina-christi* Mill. All three metabolites are being isolated for the first
18 time from the genus *Paliurus*. A model for the *in silico* binding affinity of
19 compounds **1-3** to Dipeptidyl Peptidase IV (DPP4), which is related to type 2
20 diabetes (T2D), was developed. According to our model, compounds **1-3** were
21 ranked in positions 9/12, 11/12 and 8/12, respectively and are predicted to exhibit
22 significant affinity to DPP4, in the range of low 2-digit μM .

23 Keywords: cyclopeptide alkaloids, spinachristene A, *Paliurus spina-christi*,
24 antidiabetic activity, Dipeptidyl Peptidase IV, *in silico* studies, NMR

25 1. Introduction

26 *Paliurus spina-christi* Mill. (Rhamnaceae) is a much-branched, deciduous,
27 thorny shrub found in dry slopes in the Mediterranean, Southwest and Central Asia and
28 North America (Casavecchia *et al.* 2015). It is also known as *P. aculeatus*, *P. australis*
29 and *Rhamnus paliurus*, while its common name is “Christ’s thorn”. The decoction from
30 the leaves and roots is mentioned in Dioscorides’ work "De Materia Medica" as diuretic
31 and as a treatment for poisonous bites and helpful against erysipelas (Dioscorides
32 Pedanius *et al.* 2000). Traditionally, *P. spina-christi* has been used for its diuretic,
33 antihypercholesterolemic and antidiabetic properties (Parada *et al.* 2009; Tetik *et al.*
34 2013, Takım 2021). There have been bioactivity studies on extracts from all parts of the
35 plant, concerning some of the above properties, as well as its antidiabetic, antifungal,
36 antigenotoxic, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activity (Brantner *et al.* 1996;
37 Mosaddegh *et al.* 2004; Ahmed *et al.* 2012; Zor *et al.* 2017; Şen 2018; Takım 2021;
38 Yuca *et al.* 2022; Esfahani *et al.* 2023). Phytochemical investigation of the plant species
39 belonging to the *Paliurus* genus have revealed the presence of phenolics, flavonoids,
40 catechins, terpenes, sterols and cyclopeptide alkaloids (Brantner and Maleš 1990; Lee *et*
41 *al.* 1991 and 1992; Lin *et al.* 2000; Zor *et al.* 2017; Yuca *et al.* 2022).

42 Cyclopeptide alkaloids (CPAs) are heteromonocyclic peptides consisted of a *p*-
43 or *m-ansa* cyclic system and a side chain. In the most common types, Ia and Ib, the *ansa*
44 system is composed of a *p*-oxo (Ia) or *m*-oxo (Ib) styrylamine unit, and two α -amino-
45 acid (A.A) units, the so-called ring-bound-A.A and β -hydroxyl-A.A, making up three
46 building blocks and accounting for 14-membered (Ia, *p-ansa*) or 13-membered (Ib, *m*-
47 *ansa*) ring systems. The side chain consisted of one or two A.A units (intermediary
48 A.A, N-basic terminal A.A) adds another one or two building blocks to the CPA,
49 creating the categories 4 (14) or 5 (14) for the Ia type and 4 (13) or 5 (13) for the Ib
50 type, respectively. Depending on the nature of the β -hydroxyl-A.A, Ia type is further
51 divided into subtypes Ia1 (Leu, frangulanine type), Ia2 (Phe, integerrine type) and Ia3
52 (Pro, amphibine type) (Gournelis *et al.* 1997 and 1998; Tan and Zhou 2006; Tuenter *et*
53 *al.* 2016).

54 CPAs have been reported to exhibit analgesic, sedative, anti-inflammatory,
55 antimicrobial, antifungal, antiplasmodial and cytotoxic properties, as well as activity on
56 the central nervous system, (Gournelis *et al.* 1997; Tuenter *et al.* 2016 and 2017). Three
57 CPAs, hemsine A and nummularines C and R have been tested for their *in-vitro*
58 inhibition activity against α -glycosidase and α -chymotrypsin and for their anti-glycation
59 properties (Choudhary *et al.* 2011).

60 DPP4 is a type II transmembrane protein that plays an important role in the
61 maintenance of normal glucose homeostasis by regulating the activity of glucagon-like
62 peptide-1 (GLP-1) (Deacon 2019). GLP-1 is an incretin hormone that stimulates the
63 increase of insulin secretion from pancreatic β -cells and inhibits glucagon secretion
64 after a meal, while DPP4 causes the degradation of the endogenous GLP-1 immediately
65 into inactive metabolites (Kim and Egan 2008; Röhrborn 2015). Reduced GLP-1
66 secretion or decreased response of this hormone has been observed in T2D patients

67 resulting in poor postprandial glucose homeostasis. DPP4 inhibition leads to greater
68 bioavailability of the incretin hormones that act as its substrate, thus prolonging insulin
69 secretion and activity with minimal risk of hypoglycaemia (Omar and Ahrén 2014;
70 Deacon 2019). There are currently available antidiabetic drugs, approved by FDA
71 (USA), EMA (EU) and/or PMDA (Japan), based on DPP4 inhibition, all belonging to
72 the category of gliptins (e.g. alogliptin, linagliptin, sitagliptin and teneligliptin), with
73 minor side effects (Saini *et al.* 2023). DPP4 is composed of 766 amino acids (110 kDa)
74 anchored to the membrane. Two neighbouring orthosteric and one allosteric binding
75 sites have been identified in DPP4. The active site of DPP4 lies within a large cavity
76 and includes the catalytic Ser630 and the oxyanion hole (Tyr631, Tyr547), a
77 hydrophobic S1 pocket (Tyr631, Val656, Trp659, Tyr662, Tyr666, and Val711), an S2
78 pocket and a region with saline bridging residues such as Glu205, Glu206, while there
79 is also presence of several crystal waters. The amino acids that comprise the allosteric
80 site are Arg382, Arg356, Phe357, Gly355, Ile405, Ile374, Pro359, Ser630, Glu361,
81 Arg358 (Pantaleão *et al.* 2018; Mathur *et al.* 2023).

82 The decoction of *Paliurus spina-christi* Mill. is a common element in Greek and
83 Turkish traditional remedies for T2D. Recent studies have investigated the scientific
84 basis of this traditional practice (Takım 2021). In our present work, we report on the
85 isolation of the CPAs spinachristene A (1), sanjoinenine (2), and oxyphylline C (3) (Fig.
86 1) from the methanolic extract of dried *P. spina-christi* fruits. Considering the reported
87 *in vitro* inhibition of α -glycosidase and α -chymotrypsin - enzymes associated with T2D
88 - by CPAs (Choudhary *et al.* 2011), we decided to computationally model the binding
89 affinity of **1-3** to DPP4. This work is part of our ongoing research aiming to evaluate the
90 contribution of these compounds to the reported antidiabetic properties of *P. spina-*
91 *christi* traditional decoction. Despite the existence of approved drugs that act as DPP4

92 inhibitors, the exploration of additional compounds, especially those from natural
93 sources, remains a pertinent avenue for research.

94 **2. Results and Discussion**

95 **2.1. Structure elucidation**

96 Spinachristene A (**1**) was obtained as a white powder. The molecular formula
97 $C_{28}H_{31}N_3O_4$ was determined from the $[M - H]^-$ at m/z 472.2247 amu detected in the
98 HR(-)ESIMS, indicating 15 degrees of unsaturation. The spectral data study combined
99 with a thorough literature search, allowed us to conclude that **1** was a 4(14) CPA of the
100 Ia3 subtype, with the 4 building blocks being the styrylamine unit, ILe and Pro A.A
101 units and a cinnamoyl moiety as the terminal side-chain unit of the molecule.

102 **Figure 1.**

103

104 The 1H NMR spectrum displayed signals for a methyl doublet at δ_H 0.71 (CH_3 -
105 20) and a methyl triplet at δ_H 0.86, (CH_3 -19), which had COSY cross-peaks with a
106 methine proton at δ_H 2.21 (CH-17) and with two equivalent methylene protons at δ_H
107 1.26 (CH_2 -18), respectively.

108 The above data along with a methine resonance at δ_H 4.16 (δ_C 53.1, CH-5),
109 which had COSY correlations with CH-17 and an amide proton at δ_H 6.87 (NH-6), plus
110 an HMBC cross-peak with an amide carbonyl at δ_C 166.8 (C-4), revealed the presence
111 of an ILe amino acid residue.

112 In the HSQC-DEPT spectrum, two pairs of vicinal, diastereotopic methylene
113 protons were observed, that were intercorrelated in the COSY and HMBC spectra. The
114 first one included the protons at δ_H 2.62 and δ_H 2.20 attached to a carbon at δ_C 31.9
115 (CH_{ab} -21), while the second one the protons at δ_H 3.59 and δ_H 4.06 attached to a

116 deshielded carbon at δ_C 46.7 (CH_{ab}-22). Both methylenes were part of an isolated spin
117 system, consisted of two more sp^3 methines.

118 One of them was the only oxygenated aliphatic methine in the molecule at δ_H
119 5.66 attached to a carbon at δ_C 83.4 (CH-9), typical resonances for the β -methine of the
120 β -hydroxylated A.A. unit of a CPA. It showed COSY cross-peaks with the methylene
121 protons at δ_H 2.62 and δ_H 2.20 and with the second sp^3 methine, resonating at δ_H 4.47,
122 attached to a carbon at δ_C 63.7 (CH-8), which was obviously the α -CH of this A.A.
123 residue that had no interactions with a N-H proton. These data secured that proline was
124 the β -hydroxy-A.A. unit of the molecule and consequently that ILe was the ring-bound
125 A.A. unit. This was further supported by the HMBC cross-peaks that both the α -protons
126 of Pro (H-8) and of ILe (H-5) had with the carbonyl carbon (C-7) of the Pro A.A.
127 residue at δ_C 170.5.

128 The aromatic nucleus of the styrylamine unit was identified by four doublet of
129 doublets, with characteristic *o/m* coupling constants, integrating for one proton each,
130 corresponding to four aromatic protons at δ_H 7.32 (H-12), 7.16 (H-16), 7.13 (H-15),
131 7.10 (H-13), attached to carbons at δ_C 123.1, 129.9, 130.2 and 132.5, respectively.

132 The conjugated double bond (*cis*) of the styrylamine unit was evident from the
133 signals of two sp^2 methines at δ_H 6.28 (H-1, δ_C 113.8) and at δ_H 6.76 (H-2, δ_C 125.5).
134 The olefinic methine H-2 had a COSY cross-peak with the amide proton at δ_H 6.59
135 (NH-3). The position of the styrylamine double bond was determined by the HMBC
136 correlations of H-1 with C-13, H-13 with C-1, and H-1/H-2 with C-14 (δ_C 132.5).

137 The HMBC correlations of H-13/H-15 with C-14 and H-12/H-13/H-16 with the
138 oxygenated aromatic carbon C-11 (δ_C 157.3) concluded the assignment of the *p*-
139 oxostyrylamine unit (Figures S1-S6).

140 The elucidation of the cinnamoyl moiety and the verification of its position as
141 the terminal building block of spinachristene A is described in the Supplemental
142 material.

143 Natural amino acids usually occur as L stereoisomers. In CPAs, the
144 configuration of the oxymethine C-9 must also be considered. In the vast majority of the
145 CPAs, the L-configuration for the A.A units and the *anti* stereo-relation between H-8
146 and H-9 (*erythro* relative configuration) is generally adopted, with some few exceptions
147 (Maldaner *et al.* 2011, Gehm *et al.* 2022). All Ia3 members reported in literature retain
148 the L absolute configuration for the A.A units and the *anti* stereo-relation between H-8
149 and H-9.

150 Comparison of the NMR data of compound **1** with those of Mauratine A, whose
151 structure has been established by X-ray diffraction analysis and by synthesis (Kirfel
152 1975; Cristau *et al.* 2005), Lotusines A-D (Ghedira *et al.* 1993 and 1995), Mucronine J
153 (Auvin *et al.* 1996) and Mauratine J/Amphibine E (Jossang *et al.* 1996), showed very
154 similar or almost identical resonances and $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$'s for chiral carbons and their
155 neighbouring atoms.

156 Based on these data, we adopted the absolute configuration 5S, 8S, 9S, 17S for
157 spinachristene A.

158 Compounds **2** and **3** were identified as Sanjoinenine (Abu-Zarga *et al.* 1995) and
159 Oxyphylline C (Tuenter *et al.* 2016), respectively, by comparing their NMR data with
160 those of the literature (Figures S7-S15).

161 Compounds **1-3** are members of a relatively small subgroup, called the neutral
162 CPAs. These CPAs miss a terminal A.A and have instead a non-proteinogenic acyl
163 group that acylates the N of the intermediary A.A, or directly the N of the β -OH A.A,
164 thus removing the basic properties of a normal CPA.

165 In order to distinguish them from the normal basic CPAs, we adopted the suffix
166 -ene for **1**, instead of the usual -ine, as it has been proposed in the literature (Maldaner
167 *et al.* 2011). Spinachristene A is a Ia3, 4(14) neutral CPA, sanjoinenine a Ia2, 4(14)
168 neutral CPA and oxyphylline C a Ia1, 5(14) neutral CPA.

169 **2.2. Computational modelling study on DPP4**

170 In this study, we opted to focus on the region of the two neighbouring
171 orthosteric sites, where the gliptine class of compounds binds (See Supplemental
172 Material for more information on the binding mode) (Schnapp *et al.* 2016; Berger *et al.*
173 2018).

174 There are several crystal structures available for DPP4 in the Protein Data Bank
175 (PDB) (indicatively: 1X70, Kim *et al.* 2005; 2RGU, Eckhardt *et al.* 2007; 2ONC, Feng
176 *et al.* 2007; 3G0B, Zhang *et al.* 2011; 3VJK, Yoshida *et al.* 2012). We utilized PDB:
177 3G0B for our study. Reports on experimental ligand affinities to DPP4 are much less
178 than those measuring pharmacological activity (i.e., IC₅₀). We employed the
179 experimental affinity values of dissociation constant (K_d) and free energy of binding
180 (ΔG_{bind}) of alogliptin, linagliptin, teneligliptin and sitagliptin (Schnapp *et al.* 2016) and
181 of ligands from Pan *et al.* (Pan *et al.* 2022) to evaluate our model.

182 We conducted a redocking of the bound alogliptin in 3G0B, as well as a
183 crossdocking of the bound ligand 2-((2-(3-aminopiperidin-1-yl)-4-oxoquinazolin-3(4H)-
184 yl)methyl)benzotrile in 2ONC that shares very similar SAR with alogliptin. The root
185 mean square deviations (RMSD) of heavy atoms are 0.53 Å in both cases (Fig S16,
186 S17), which indicates a robust protocol. We continued by crossdocking sitagliptin
187 (PDB: 1X70, RMSD: 1.75 Å, Fig S18), linagliptin (PDB: 2RGU, RMSD: 2.52 Å, Fig
188 S19) and teneligliptin (PDB: 3VJK, RMSD: 1.62 Å, Fig S20). These additional
189 crossdockings with approved gliptin drugs illustrate that our model is robust enough to

190 accommodate ligands with high structural variety, thereby we continued with the
191 docking of ligands from Pan *et al.*. It is noteworthy to mention that during the docking
192 we kept one crystal water which was conserved in three crystal structures (3G0B:
193 HOH8 superimposed with 2ONC: HOH838, 1X70: HOH1551, 3VJK: HOH2018) and
194 evaluated its thermodynamic profile (Watermap – Schrodinger Platform) whereby it is
195 shown that it contributes positively to the stability of the system (Table S2).

196 The correlation between the docking score and the experimental K_d values of the
197 ligands was $r^2 = 0.60$ (Fig S21). To improve the model, we rescored the docking poses
198 using Molecular Mechanics with Generalised Born and Surface Area solvation
199 (MMGBSA) (Tuccinardi 2021). The correlation between MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} and K_d
200 values was $r^2 = 0.67$ (Fig S22) and the correlation between MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} and
201 experimental ΔG_{bind} was $r^2 = 0.78$ (Fig S23), which is significantly better. Since ΔG_{bind}
202 was employed as a measure of affinity, the ΔG Predictive Index (PI) of the model was
203 calculated: $PI = 0.64$ (Table S3) (Pearlman and Charifson 2001). The PI ranges between
204 +1 and -1, with +1 expressing that the calculated ΔG ranking is in accordance with the
205 experimental one, -1 expressing it is reverse, and 0 indicating that there is no correlation
206 between the two. The aforementioned r^2 and PI values suggest that our model exhibits a
207 very good correlation and a good predictive capacity.

208 After the model evaluation, compounds **1-3** passed through the docking and
209 MMGBSA pipeline and were ranked in positions 9/12, 11/12 and 8/12, respectively,
210 (Table 1). According to our model, this ranking indicates that compounds **1-3** are
211 expected to exhibit a K_d in the region of low 2-digit μM affinity to DPP4. Furthermore,
212 based on the excellent correlation of MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} to IC_{50} ($r^2 = 0.98$; Fig S24), if
213 compounds **1-3** are DPP4 antagonists, it is anticipated that they should have $IC_{50} < 200$
214 μM , characterizing them as potential hit compounds.

215 The extrapolated SAR from compounds **1** and **2** show that hydrogen bonds are
216 formed with Tyr547 (**2**) and Glu205 (**1**). Furthermore, π - π stacking interactions take
217 place in compounds **1** and **3** with Tyr666 (both), Tyr547 (only **1**), while **2** forms a π -
218 cation interaction with Arg560 (Figures 2 and S25 and S26).

219 **Table 1**

220

221 **Figure 2.**

222 **3. Experimental**

223 **1.**

224 **2.**

225 **3.**

226 ***3.1. Plant material***

227 Mature fruits of *Paliurus spina-christi* Mill. were collected in November 2020 in
228 Dafnospilia in Karditsa region (Central Greece). The plant was identified by
229 agriculturist Dr. E. Kalpoutzakis (NKUA). A voucher specimen, VA-001/15-11-2020,
230 has been deposited in the herbarium of Pharmacognosy Laboratory of University of
231 Athens.

232 ***3.2. General experimental procedures***

233 The detailed description is provided in the Supplemental Material.

234 ***3.3. Extraction and isolation***

235 The detailed description is provided in the Supplemental Material.

3.4. Spectral data

237 **Spinachristene A (1):** Yellow powder (0.5 mg); HR(-)ESIMS m/z 472.2247 [M - H]⁻
238 (calcd for C₂₈H₃₀N₃O₄⁻, 472.2242, $\Delta m = 1$ ppm); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{H} 7.62
239 (1H, d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, H-26), 7.51 (2H, m, H-28/32), 7.37 (3H, m, H-29/30/31), 7.32 (1
240 H, dd, $J = 8.4/2.3$ Hz, H-12), 7.16 (1H, dd, $J = 8.1/2.3$ Hz, H-16), 7.13 (1H, dd, $J =$
241 8.1/1.8 Hz, H-15), 7.10 (1H, dd, $J = 8.3/1.8$ Hz, H-13), 6.87 (1H, d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, NH-6),
242 6.76 (1H, dd, $J = 10.6/7.9$ Hz, H-2), 6.64 (1H, d, $J = 15.5$ Hz, H-25), 6.59 (1H, d, $J =$
243 10.6 Hz, NH-3), 6.28 (1H, d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, H-1), 5.66 (1H, ddd, $J = 10.0/7.1/5.6$ Hz, H-
244 9), 4.47 (1H, d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, H-8), 4.16 (1H, ddd, $J = 8.4/3.0$ Hz, H-5), 4.06 (1H, dd, $J =$
245 10.9/8.5 Hz, H-22b), 3.59 (1H, ddd, $J = 12.8/10.9/5.5$ Hz, H-22a), 2.62 (1H, ddd, $J =$
246 12.3/7.1/5.5 Hz, H-21b), 2.21 (1H, ovlp by H-21a, H-17), 2.20 (1H, ovlp by H-17, H-
247 21a), 1.26 (2H, m, H-18a,b), 0.86 (3H, t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, H-19), 0.70 (3H, d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, H-
248 20); ¹³C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl₃) δ_{C} 170.5 (C-7), 166.8 (C-4), 165.7 (C-24), 157.3 (C-
249 11), 143.5 (C-26), 134.4 (C-27), 132.5 (C-13), 132.5 (C-14), 130.2 (C-15), 130.3 (C-
250 30), 129.0 (C-29/31), 128.0 (C-28/32), 125.5 (C-2), 123.1 (C-12), 122.9 (C-16), 116.9
251 (C-25), 113.8 (C-1), 83.4 (C-9), 63.7 (C-8), 59.1 (C-5), 46.7 (C-22), 35.0 (C-17), 31.9
252 (C-21), 23.0 (C-18), 15.7 (C-20), 12.3 (C-19).

253

3.5. Computational Chemistry

254 All protein and ligand preparation, docking and free energy calculations, as well
255 as the analysis of the poses were conducted using the Schrödinger platform, LLC, New
256 York, NY, release 2019-1. Ligand preparation was performed with LigPrep using Epik
257 (Shelley *et al.* 2007; Greenwood *et al.* 2010) to generate protonation states at pH = 7.4 ±
258 2.0. From the four chains in 3G0B, chain A was employed. Protein preparation was
259 performed using Protein Preparation Wizard, with Prime to fill in missing side chains
260 and loops, capping termini, removing water molecules (except water HOH8), and Epik

261 to generate protonation states at $\text{pH} = 7.4 \pm 2.0$. The docking grid was created using the
262 Receptor Grid Generation module of Glide. Rigid docking was performed with Glide,
263 with the use of XP scoring (extra precision), performing post docking minimization and
264 applying strain correction terms. The MMGBSA free energy of binding calculation was
265 performed using Prime. The structure-activity relationships (SAR), such as hydrogen
266 bonds, π - π interactions etc. were identified automatically using Maestro. The PI index
267 was calculated using the formula described in Table S3. Detailed information on the
268 protocols can be found in the Supplemental Material.

269 **4. Conclusions**

270 The examination of phytochemical constituents in the dried fruits of *Paliurus*
271 *spina-christi* has yielded three cyclopeptide alkaloids. Compound **1** is a novel natural
272 product, while compounds **2** and **3** are identified for the first time within the genus
273 *Paliurus*. A computational model has been developed to assess the binding affinity of
274 these CPAs with DPP4, for the first time.

275 Considering the outcomes of this research and drawing insights from the
276 ethnopharmacological applications of *P. spina-christi*, a more comprehensive
277 investigation of the possible inhibition of CPAs against DPP4 and other targets involved
278 in the biochemical pathology of T2D *in vitro* is needed. While our findings suggest their
279 binding capacity to DPP4, further exploration is essential to delineate their exact
280 binding mode and potential beneficial roles in T2D.

281 **Disclosure statement**

282 The authors declare no potential conflict of interest

283

284 **Acknowledgements**

285 A.D. acknowledges funding from the European Union's horizon 2020 research and
286 innovationprogramm under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 945380.

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Table 1. Computational model ranking.

	Exp. ΔG (kcal/mol)	Docking Score	MMGBSA ΔG (kcal/mol)	Kd (nM)	IC ₅₀ (nM)
Alogliptin (3G0B)	-10.35	-9.879	-53	2.4	6.9
Linagliptin	-11.4	-7.041	-46.62	0.0066	0.97
Teneligliptin	-10.84	-4.674	-44.7	0.41	48
Sitagliptin	-10.74	-8.182	-39.19	5.3	18
Narcissoside	-8.0593	-8.55	-29.16	1230	166520
Isoliquiritigenin	-6.4508	-5.044	-27.46	18587	149960
Cyanidin 3-O-glucoside	-6.5774	-6.829	-27.09	14992	81050
Oxyphylline C (3)		-4.599	-20.32		
Spinachristene A (1)		-3.024	-16.1		
Hyperoside	-6.6334	-6.127	-13.05	13661	138790
Sanjoinenine (2)		-2.895	-12.63		
Myricetin	-6.0564	-2.223	-6.19	36232	1546290

Figure 1. Structures of the isolated cyclopeptide alkaloids from *Paliurus spina-christi*.

Figure 2. Suggested binding mode and SAR of Compound 1 (Spinachristene A)

1 **SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL**

2 **Cyclopeptide alkaloids from the Greek shrub *Paliurus spina-christi***
3 **and their *in silico* binding affinity to Dipeptidyl Peptidase IV.**

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13

14 **ABSTRACT**

15 A new cyclopeptide alkaloid, spinachristene A (**1**), along with two previously
16 described, sanjoinenine (**2**) and oxyphylline C (**3**), were isolated from the fruits of
17 *Paliurus spina-christi* Mill. All three metabolites are being isolated for the first
18 time from the genus *Paliurus*. A model for the *in silico* binding affinity of
19 compounds **1-3** to Dipeptidyl Peptidase IV (DPP4), which is related to type 2
20 diabetes (T2D), was developed. According to our model, compounds **1-3** were
21 ranked in positions 9/12, 11/12 and 8/12, respectively and are predicted to exhibit
22 significant affinity to DPP4, in the range of low 2-digit μM .

23 Keywords: cyclopeptide alkaloids, spinachristene A, *Paliurus spina-christi*,
24 antidiabetic activity, DPP4, *in silico* studies, NMR

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74 2. Results and Discussion (Additional information)

75 2.1. Structure elucidation

76 The cinnamoyl moiety was identified by the presence of two groups of protons in the
77 $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum. The first one included the doublets at δ_{H} 6.64 (H-25, d, $^3J = 15.0$, δ_{C}
78 116.9) and at δ_{H} 7.62 (H-26, d, $^3J = 15.0$, δ_{C} 143.5) accounting for a conjugated *trans*
79 double bond. The second group included two aromatic multiplets, with the first one at
80 δ_{H} 7.51, integrating for two equivalent protons, (H-28/H-32, m, δ_{C} 28/32 128.0) and the
81 second one at δ_{H} 7.37 integrating for three protons (H-29/H-31, m, and H-30, m, δ_{C} 29/31
82 129.0, δ_{C} 30 130.3). The HMBC cross-peaks of H-28/H-32 with C-26 at δ_{C} 143.5,
83 distinguished the two pairs of equivalent aromatic protons of the cinnamoyl moiety.
84 Finally, the position of the cinnamoyl moiety as the terminal-building block of the
85 molecule and its amidic linkage with the β -hydroxyl-Pro unit was confirmed by the
86 HMBC correlations of H-25/H-26/H-8 with the carbonyl of the cinnamate at δ_{C} 165.7
87 (C-24).

88 2.2. Computational modelling study on DPP4

89 In the gliptine binding mode, the hydrophobic S1 pocket of DPP4 is filled by
90 hydrophobic inhibitor moieties, while the S2 pocket is occupied by other substituents.
91 Further general SAR of the gliptines include an amino group interaction with the
92 recognition site for the peptide substrate N-terminus (Glu205, Glu206, and Tyr662).
93 Specific interactions with the other regions of the binding pocket vary for the different
94 inhibitors, which is expected given the big structural differences between the members
95 of the gliptine class (Schnapp et al. 2016; Berger et al. 2018 Devasthale et al. 2013;
96 Nabeno et al. 2013).

97 **3. Experimental (Additional information)**

98 **3.1. General experimental procedures**

99 1D/2D NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer equipped with
100 a 5mm PABBI 1 H/D-BB inverse detection probe (1H/13C, 600 MHz/150 MHz,
101 Bruker, Zurich, Switzerland). Chemical shifts (δ) were expressed in ppm. HRESIMS
102 spectra were obtained on an ESI-LTQ Orbitrap Discovery XL spectrometer (Thermo
103 Scientific, USA). Semi-preparative HPLC was performed on a Thermo Finnigan
104 SpectraSystem setup (Thermo Finnigan, USA) using a Viridis Silica column (250 mm \times
105 4.6 mm, 5 μ m). Column chromatography (CC) was performed with silica gel 60H (40-
106 60 μ m, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Column fractions were monitored by TLC (0.1
107 mm layer thickness, silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), and the spots
108 were visualized by heating the plates after spraying with the vanillin sulfuric acid
109 reagent. Preparative TLC (0.5 mm layer thickness, silica gel 60 F₂₅₄, E. Merck,
110 Darmstadt, Germany) was used for fractionation of some samples. All reagents were of
111 HPLC grade and purchased from Merck.

112 **1.**

113 **2.**

114 **3.**

115 **3.1.**

116 **3.2.**

117 **3.2. Extraction and isolation**

118 The fruits of *P. spina-christi* were air-dried, grounded to 766 g of powder and extracted

119 twice with cyclohexane (c-Hex), dichloromethane (DCM), methanol (MeOH) and
120 water, consecutively, by maceration. After evaporating the organic solvents, the
121 remaining water was removed by lyophilization to yield 19.8 g (2.6%), 5.8 g (0.8%),
122 11.7 g (1.5%) and 6.1 g (0.8%) of dry extracts, respectively. A part of the methanol dry
123 extract (5.92 g) was fractionated by sequentially treatment with c-hex, ethyl acetate
124 (EtOAc), MeOH and water to yield fractions of 322 mg, 654 mg, 1.5 g and 3.4 g,
125 respectively. The EtOAc fraction was fractionated by silica gel column
126 chromatography, eluted with c-Hex-EtOAc-MeOH (95:5:0, 90:10:0, 0:100:0, 0:90:10,
127 0:85:15) to obtain eight fractions (Fr. 1-8). Fraction 7 (59.2 mg) was chromatographed
128 on preparative TLC (EtOAc-MeOH 90:10, v/v) to obtain four subfractions (Fr. C1-C4).
129 Subfraction C3 (9.3 mg) was subjected to semi-preparative NP HPLC (c-Hex-
130 isopropanol 85:15, v/v, 1 mL/min) to yield sanjoinine (**2**, 1.3 mg, $t_R = 9$ min) and
131 oxyphylline C (**3**, 2.1 mg, $t_R = 15$ min). Subfraction C4 (3.6 mg) was also subjected to
132 semi-preparative NP HPLC (c-Hex-EtOAc 60:40, v/v, 1 mL/min) to yield
133 spinachristene A (**1**, 0.5 mg, $t_R = 15$ min).

134 **1.**

135 **2.**

136 **3.**

137 **3.1.**

138 **3.2.**

139 **3.3.**

140 **3.4.**

141 **3.5. Computational Chemistry**

142 All protein and ligand preparation, docking and free energy calculations, as well as the
143 analysis of the poses were conducted using the Schrödinger platform, LLC, New York,
144 NY, release 2019-1. The 3D ligand structures were constructed using the relevant
145 SMARTS patterns from PubChem, except for ligand structures which were extracted
146 from cited PDB crystal structures. Ligand preparation was performed with the default
147 protocol of LigPrep using Epik (Shelley *et al.* 2007; Greenwood *et al.* 2010) to generate
148 protonation states at $\text{pH} = 7.4 \pm 2.0$. Due to the strictly defined stereocenters of the
149 natural products under examination, we commanded the program to retain all specified
150 chiralities. From the four chains in 3G0B, chain A was employed and the rest were
151 deleted. Protein preparation was performed using the default protocol of Protein
152 Preparation Wizard, using Prime to fill in missing side chains and loops, capping
153 termini, removing water molecules (except water HOH8), and Epik to generate
154 protonation states at $\text{pH} = 7.4 \pm 2.0$. The docking grid was created using the Receptor
155 Grid Generation module of Glide at default settings, with the grid forming an enclosing

156 box with dimensions 10 Å x 10 Å x 10 Å with the centroid of the crystal bound ligand
157 as its centre.

158 The list of the amino acids comprising the grid (PDB: 3G0B, chain A) is: Ser209,
159 Glu205, Arg125, Asn710, Hid740, Val711, Tyr662, Trp659, Val656, ser630, Trp629,
160 Tyr631, Gly632, Tyr547, Lys554, Gly549, Pro550, Tyr670, Phe357, Arg669, Tyr666,
161 Gln715, Arg560, Tyr585, Arg356, Arg358, Gln53, Ser552, Cys551, Trp353, Ala210,
162 Phe208, Hid126, Gly741, Trp124, Trp201, Asp739, Tyr365, Val207, Trp627, Ala652,
163 Gly628, Ala548, Val202, Leu598, Ile594, Asp663, Gly204, Val665, Val546, Asp545,
164 Tyr634, Ala259, Lys258, Asp709, Asp708, Gly632, Gly633, Ala654, Pro655, Val635,
165 Thr667, Ser664.

166 Rigid docking was performed with the default protocol of Glide, with the use of XP
167 scoring (extra precision), performing post docking minimization and applying strain
168 correction terms. The MMGBSA free energy of binding calculation was performed
169 using the default protocol of Prime. The structure-activity relationships (SAR), such as
170 hydrogen bonds, π - π interactions etc. were identified automatically using the default
171 settings of Maestro. The PI index was calculated using the formula described in Table
172 S3.

173

174 Table S1. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopic data[#] for compounds **2** and **3** (600 MHz and
175 150 MHz), in CDCl_3

Position	2		3	
	δ_{H} (ppm) (<i>J</i> in Hz)	δ_{C} (ppm)	δ_{H} (ppm) (<i>J</i> in Hz)	δ_{C} (ppm)
1	6.36, 1H, d, (7.8)	116.5	6.38, 1H, d, (7.7)	116.5
2	6.64, 1H, dd, (10.0 / 7.8)	126.0	6.72, 1H, t, (9.8 / 7.7)	126.2
3-NH	6.48, 1H, d, (10.0)		6.57, 1H, d, (9.8)	
4		n.d.		169.8
5	4.05, 1H, ddd, (11.0 / 7.5 /	53.2	3.89, 1H, br d, (7.2)	59.6

	3.2)			
6-NH	5.86, 1H, d, (7.5)			
7		n.d.		170.4
8	4.68, 1H, dd, (10.2 / 7.3)	55.6	4.74, 1H, dd, (9.7 / 7.0)	56.3
9	4.99, 1H, dd, (7.3 / 1.6)	81.9	5.92, 1H, d, (7.0)	82.4
11		n.d.		155.0
12	7.16 ^a , 1H, dd, (8.5 / 2.8)	123.4	7.32, 1H, (ovlp)	124.2
13	7.07 ^a , 1H, dd, (8.2 / 3.0)	132.2	7.11, 1H, (ovlp)	132.7
14		n.d.		131.7
15	7.06 ^a , 1H, dd, (8.2 / 3.0)	130.9	7.06, 1H, (ovlp)	131.0
16	7.19 ^a , 1H, dd, 8.5 / 2.8)	122.8	7.21, 1H, (ovlp)	124.0
17a	1.28, 1H, (ovlp)		1.4, 1H, (ovlp)	
17b	1.74, 1H, ddd, (14.0 / 10.7 / 3.3)	39.5	2.21, 1H, dd, (12.1 / 6.3)	26.1
18a	1.26, 1H, m	20.5	1.53, 1H, (ovlp)	24.8
18b			1.81, 1H, m	
19a	0.58, 3H, d, (6.6)	20.8	3.01, 1H, br.t, (8.3)	47.3
19b			3.2, 1H, td, (9.6 / 7.0)	
20	0.71, 3H, d, (6.6)	23.5		136.8
21	2, 1H, m	29.8	7.33, 2H, m	128.9
22	0.99, 3H, d, (6.7)	14.6	7.19, 2H, (ovlp)	127.8
23	1.27, 3H, d, (6.7)	20.6	7.22, 1H, (ovlp)	124.1
24	5.90, 1H, d, (10.2)		7.19, 2H, (ovlp)	127.8
25		n.d.	7.33, 2H, m	128.9
26	6.28, 1H, d, (15.5)	119.2	7.48, 1H, (ovlp)	-
27	7.60, 1H, d, (15.5)	143.9		166.4
28		n.d.	4.54, 1H, m	54.4
29a	7.46 ^b , 2H, (ovlp)	128.4	2.77, 1H, dd, (15.5 / 10.0)	36.3
29b			3.34, 1H, dd, (15.5 / 3.6)	36.3
30	7.37 ^b , 2H, (ovlp)	129.4		136.2
31	7.37, 1H, (ovlp)	131	7.10, 2H, (ovlp)	128.1
32	7.37, 2H, (ovlp)	129.4	7.06, 2H, (ovlp)	129.3
33	7.46 ^b , 2H, (ovlp)	128.4	7.20, 1H, (ovlp)	129.0
34			7.06, 2H, (ovlp)	129.3
35			7.10, 2H, (ovlp)	128.1
36-NH			5.88, 1H, d, (7.5)	
37				165.7
38			6.25, 1H, d, (15.5)	118.0
39			7.48, 1H, d, (15.5)	144.0
40				134.6
41/45			7.52, 2H, dd, (8.0 / 1.9 Hz)	128.6
42/44			7.42, 2H, m	129.7

176 a,b Chemical shifts on the same column with the same superscript may be interchanged.
177 # The connection of protons with their carbons was based on the HSQC-DEPT
178 experiment.
179 ovp: overlapped.

180

181 Figure S1. ¹H NMR spectrum of Compound 1 (Spinachristene A)

182

183

184 Figure S2. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of Compound 1 (Spinachristene A)

185

186 Figure S3. HSQC spectrum of Compound 1 (Spinachristene A)

187

188

189 Figure S4. HMBC spectrum of Compound 1 (Spinachristene A)

190

191

192 Figure S5. ^1H - ^1H COSY correlations (bold lines) and key HMBC correlations (red

193 arrows) of spinachristene A (**1**)

194

PSC_D_P5_12_4_17_ESI(-) #2 RT: 0.01 AV: 1 NL: 2.98E5
T: FTMS - c ESI Full ms [100.00-1000.00]

195

196 Figure S6. HR(-)ESIMS spectrum of Compound 1 (Spinachristene A)

197

198

199 Figure S7. ^1H NMR spectrum of Compound 2 (Sanjoinenine)

200

201

202 Figure S8. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of Compound 2 (Sanjoinenine)

203

204 Figure S9. HSQC spectrum of Compound 2 (Sanjoinenine)

205

PSC_C_P2_12_4_17_ESI(-) #1 RT: 0.00 AV: 1 NL: 3.52E6
T: FTMS - c ESI Full ms [100.00-1000.00]

206

207 Figure S10. HR(-)ESIMS spectrum of Compound 2 (Sanjoinenine, $[M-H]^-$ 488.2562

208 amu, calc. 488.2555, $\Delta m=1.4$ ppm)

209

210

211 Figure S11. ^1H NMR spectrum of Compound 3 (Oxyphylline C)

212

213

214 Figure S12. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of Compound 3 (Oxyphylline C)

215

216 Figure S13. HSQC spectrum of Compound 3 (Oxyphylline C)

217

218

219 Figure S14. HMBC spectrum of Compound 3 (Oxyphylline C)

PSC_C_P7_12_4_17_ESI(-) #1 RT: 0.01 AV: 1 NL: 5.63E6
T: FTMS - c ESI Full ms [100.00-1000.00]

221

222 Figure S15. HR(-)ESIMS spectrum of Compound 3 (Oxyphylline C, $[M-H]^-$ 653.2786
223 amu, calc. 653.2769, $\Delta m=2.6$ ppm)

224

225

226 Figure S16. Alogliptin redock (green: crystal; pink: docking pose). RMSD: 0.53 Å
227 (3G0B, heavy atoms)

228

229

230 Figure S17. 2ONC crossdock (yellow: crystal bound; violet: docking pose). RMSD:
231 0.53 Å, (2ONC, heavy atoms)

232

233

234 Figure S18. Sitagliptin crossdock (blue: crystal bound; magenta: docking pose). RMSD:
235 1.75 Å (1X70, heavy atoms)

236

237

238 Figure S19. Linagliptin crossdock (purple: crystal bound; orange: docking pose).
239 RMSD: 2.52 Å (2RGU, heavy atoms)

240

241

242 Figure S20. Teneeligiptin crossdock (red: crystal bound; cyan: docking pose). RMSD:
 243 1.62 Å (3VJK, heavy atoms)

244

245 Table S2 Watermap results*

PDB: 3G08	ΔG (kcal/mol)	ΔH (kcal/mol)	$-T\Delta S$ (kcal/mol)	# H-bonds protein- water	# H-bonds in crystal
HOH8	-0.11	-4.85	4.74	2.62	Glu206, Arg669 (2)

246 *WaterMap is a molecular dynamics-based computational method that uses statistical
 247 mechanics to describe the thermodynamic properties (entropy, enthalpy, and free energy) of
 248 water molecules at the surface of proteins. This method can be used to assess the solvent
 249 contributions to ligand binding affinity and to guide lead optimization (Cappel *et al.* 2017).
 250

251

252 Figure S21. Correlation between the docking score and the experimental K_d values of
 253 the ligands

254

255

256 Figure S22. Correlation between MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} and K_d values. Since ΔG and K_d are
 257 connected through the equation $\Delta G = RT \ln K_d$, the y axis with K_d values is presented in
 258 a logarithmic scale.

259

260

261 Figure S23. Correlation between MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} and experimental ΔG_{bind}

262

263 Table S3. Calculation of PI index*

$E(j) - E(i)$	W_{ij}	$P(j) - P(i)$	$[E(j) - E(i)]/[P(j) - P(i)]$	C_{ij}	$C_{ij} * W_{ij}$	$E(j) - E(i)$
$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{exp}}$	$ \Delta\Delta G_{\text{exp}} $	$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{MGBSA}}$	$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{exp}} / \Delta\Delta G_{\text{MMGBSA}}$	C	$C * \Delta\Delta G_{\text{exp}} $	$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{exp}}$
2-1	-1.05	1.05	6.38	-0.164576803	-1	-1.05
3-2	0.56	0.56	1.92	0.291666667	1	0.56
4-3	0.1	0.1	5.51	0.01814882	1	0.1
5-4	2.6807	2.6807	10.03	0.267268195	1	2.6807
6-5	1.6085	1.6085	1.7	0.946176471	1	1.6085
7-6	-0.1266	0.1266	0.37	-0.342162162	-1	-0.1266
8-7	-0.056	0.056	14.04	-0.003988604	-1	-0.056

9-8	0.577	0.577	6.86	0.084110787	1	0.577
Sum	4.2936	6.7588	46.81			4.2936
					PI =	0.63526 0697

264

265 *Calculation of PI Index

266
$$PI = \frac{\sum_{j>i} \sum_i w_{ij} C_{ij}}{\sum_{j>i} \sum_i w_{ij}}$$

267
$$w_{ij} = |E(j) - E(i)|$$

268
$$C_{ij} = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } \frac{E(j) - E(i)}{P(j) - P(i)} < 0 \\ +1 & \text{if } \frac{E(j) - E(i)}{P(j) - P(i)} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } P(j) - P(i) = 0 \end{cases}$$

269 E(i) = Experimental ΔG_{bind} of compound i.

270 P(i) = Predicted ΔG_{bind} of compound i.

271

272

273 Figure S24. Correlation between MMGBSA ΔG_{bind} and IC_{50}

274

275 Figure S25. Suggested binding mode and SAR of Compound 2 (Sanjoinenine)

276

277

278 Figure S26. Suggested binding mode and SAR of Compound 3 (Oxyphylline C)

279

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